

OVERVIEW OF FACTORS AFFECTING FRAUDULENT BEHAVIOR IN FINANCIAL STATEMENTS OF ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

This study aims to overview the factors affecting the fraudulent behavior of financial statements of enterprises, on the basis of the Cressey (1953) Fraud Triangle Theory. Through the synthesis and analysis of data sources from predecessor studies, the article considers the impact of the following groups of factors: Motivation/pressure; Opportunity; and Attitude to influence fraudulent behavior on the financial statements of enterprises. The article contributes to providing a comprehensive review of academic research related to the factor groups: Motivation/pressure; Opportunity; and Attitude, thereby providing direction for future empirical research. At the same time, the study also elicits experience and implications for stakeholders in detecting, preventing and reducing fraudulent behavior on the financial statements of enterprises.

Keywords: Financial statements, fraud, fraudulent behavior, fraud triangle.

1. INTRODUCTION

Accounting is the language of business, which is considered as a partial summary of what managers in the business want to convey to investors, relevant agencies and the public. Products of accounting are financial statements prepared, presented and published to meet the requirements of content and form, especially the truthfulness and appropriateness of information. Although prepared by accountants, senior managers in the business are most responsible for the financial statements for the truthfulness and reasonableness of the information it reflects. In fact, it is not always and when the financial statements of the enterprise reflect the actual financial performance of the enterprise, or in other words, the financial statements of the enterprise are published may contain frauds, which causes the interested persons to misinterpret and the economic decisions they make based on false information are wrong decisions.

In recent years, there have been various scandals around the world related to lack of transparency in information disclosure, financial reporting manipulation and have caused many very disturbing consequences, such as: According to the results of an investigation by the Association of American Fraud Investigators (ACFE) published in 2019, the annual loss of fraud is estimated at more than \$5,000 billion worldwide, and each reported case of fraud causes an average loss to the business of more than \$100,000 and it takes about 16 months to investigate and detect fraud. In particular, in the Asia Pacific countries, the average loss is more than 236,000 US dollars. More dangerous than that, it creates a fraudulent flow that severely erodes the trust of those who care. Typical cases can be mentioned, such as: Dell Company - 2006; Samsung Group 2016; Toshiba Group of Japan has "bewitched" to turn losses into

profits, pushing the financial shortfall amount up to \$1.2 billion braked in 2015; or the story of Enron and Lehman Brothers has become very famous.

Mistakes in the financial statements in general and frauds in particular, usually the disappearance of accounting data, the appropriateness of financial information used by the owners or managers in the enterprise to mislead the financial situation and business results in their favor. This is not too difficult to do, especially for administrators who are knowledgeable about finance and accounting. Many questions have been asked to find out, such as: What factors have influenced the fraudulent behavior in the financial statements? How can fraud be mitigated in the financial statements of businesses?

Studies on fraud in financial operations, accounting in general and factors affecting fraudulent behavior on financial statements in particular have been carried out in many countries and are mainly based on the theory of the fraud triangle (Fraud Triangle) Cressey (1953). According to the school of fraud triangulation theory, Graham & Bedard (2003) reflected in the study that the perception of factors affecting fraudulent behavior often related to the attitude and personality of managers is more important than other factors. Moyes et al., (2005) argue that the factors that lead to the motivation of fraud relate to the attitude factor (the factor that has a history of violation of the law or violation of securities laws, allegations of fraud against board members or senior directors) more effectively than the factors of opportunity and pressure in detecting fraud. Abdullatif (2013), argued that the motives for fraud stem from the attitude of managers is more important than the factors of opportunity and pressure. Skousen & Wright (2006) identified 5 motivational/pressure factors, and 2 opportunistic factors that have a statistically significant relationship with the likelihood of fraud in the financial statements. These factors were also tested based on the evaluation of many studies (Othman & Zeghal, 2006; Lou & Wang, 2009; Li, 2010; Lord, 2010; Marinakis, 2011; Rezaee & Riley, 2011; Fathi, 2013) and other documents and evidence.

Therefore, fraud on financial statements of enterprises is an argument that attracts a lot of attention and attention of academics and practical activities. Based on the literature review, the main purpose of this article is to identify the factors affecting fraudulent behavior in financial statements of enterprises as the basis for the assessment and measurement of those factors in specific contexts.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Overview of the concept of fraud on the financial statements

In the field of finance and accounting, the term fraud on financial statements is understood to mean fraud committed or colluded with by managers. Therefore, the term fraud on the financial statements can be referred to as managerial fraud.

According to Elliott & Willingham (1980), fraud in the financial statements is a deliberate fraud committed by a manager, harming investors and creditors through material misrepresentation of information in the financial statements. In addition, Wells (2011) argues that fraud in the financial statements is intentional errors such as intentionally omitting data or

explanatory information in the financial statements to deceive users of the financial statements, especially investors and creditors.

Albrecht et al., (2012) argue that fraud is a deceptive act aimed at personal gain, in this view fraud is understood as the dishonest actions of individuals to protect their own interests.

According to Ernst & Young (2009), fraud is an intentional act committed by a person or group of people knowing that errors may result in some improper benefit to the individual or the organization. This view also emphasizes intentional behavior, that is, intentional behavior, whose purpose is that the performer becomes aware that it results in unlawful benefits. Unlike the view of Albrecht et al., (2012) this concept emphasizes that the subject causing the fraud is not only the individual but also a group of people.

Thus, it is possible to see the common characteristics in the concepts of fraudulent acts on the financial statements, namely: Fraudulent acts on the financial statements are deliberate acts of the managers in order to falsify the information on the financial statements, causing harm to investors and creditors.

2.2. Overview of factors affecting fraudulent behavior in financial statements

On the basis of the Cressey fraud triangle theory (1953), fraud is only committed when the following three factors are fully converged: pressure, opportunity, and human attitude.

2.2.1. Motor/ pressure factor group

Financial stability

In an increasingly volatile market economy, enterprises are always under pressure from objective and subjective causes such as political instability, natural disasters, high competition from competitors, rapid changes in technical technology while the business market is saturated and the demand for products of customer's declines... According to the asymmetric information theory, when companies in the same industry report less optimistic financial situation, some companies still report high growth and unusually high business results, or business continuity losses, but some companies still report high profit and growth business (Bell & Carcello, 2000, Graham & Bedard, 2003, Abullatif (2013). That proves that some companies are motivated to commit fraud on the financial statements. Studies by Albrecht et al., (1986), Bell & Carcello (2000), Gramling & Myres (2003), Moyes et al., (2005), Mock & Turner (2005), Smith et al., (2005), Skousen & Wright (2006) all suggest that abnormal fluctuations from the economic situation, business lines of the unit negatively impact the business results of the business even leading to the risk of bankruptcy. Therefore, in order to maintain the stability of the financial situation, the company's management must make adjustments to the financial statements in a positive direction in favor of the company. It was this that motivated the fraudulent conduct on the financial statements to occur.

Financial stability can be measured through the following five assessment criteria (Skousen & Wright, 2006; Lou & Wang, 2009):

- (1) Average asset growth rate of 2 consecutive years before fraud year.
- (2) Difference in profit from operating activities.
- (3) Loss of previous year adjoining.
- (4) Continuously incurred negative cash flow.
- (5) Gross profit ratio.

Pressure from third parties

The pressure also comes from the fact that business management can be subjected to a lot of pressure from shareholders and investors, especially at difficult times. The pressure of gross profit rate and the overly optimistic and unrealistic expectations of investors about the positive business situation put pressure on the board of directors in meeting these expectations and the financial statements may be misrepresented; Pressure to meet the requirements of listing and issuing shares or raising capital from banks, or some major shareholders plan to divest from the company. If these expectations are too high, it will put pressure on management to create incentives to commit fraud on financial statements to meet these expectations (Moyes, 2007; Abullatif, 2013).

If the business situation is in a difficult situation, there is a risk of bankruptcy or shrinking the business scale, leading to losses, but usually, businesses still want a good financial statement to please investors (Moyes, 2007; Abullatif, 2013). The legal conditions for listed companies before listing and issuing additional shares, maintaining the number of shareholders is the pressure for listed companies to adjust the profitability indicators or change the financial structure to increase the financial capacity of listed companies (Moyes, 2007; Abullatif, 2013). All of this can put pressure on management to produce a fraudulent financial statement.

Pressure from third parties is expressed by the following criteria (Lou & Wang, 2009; Persons, 1995; Skousen & Wright, 2006):

- (1) The pressure from the debt balance lever.
- (2) Pressure from self-financing.
- (3) Pressure from the need to raise capital.

Financial objectives

Financial objectives are also seen as one of the drivers of fraudulent behavior in financial statements. The financial objectives set by the management board... are an important factor affecting the fraudulent behavior on the financial statements of the business. Industry environment has changed a lot in the direction of disadvantage or positive for the business: when there are changes in market demand, competition and macro factors affecting the business plan of the business, the business will tend to technical handling of financial statements in order to achieve the assigned business objectives (Moyes, 2007; Abullatif, 2013). According to the asymmetric information theory, in order to survive and continue to receive support from investors, banks providing capital, enterprises will tend to prepare financial

statements to increase profit/decrease loss. In addition, the income structure, salary and bonus of the management if it depends heavily on the financial results of the enterprise, it will be the motivation for the management to adjust the financial statements in a better direction to receive higher income. The greater the reward ratio from business results, the higher the motivation to increase business results will be and vice versa. In order to promote the motivation to develop production and business, enterprises now tend to increase the income ratio for employees, especially senior leaders associated with the business results of the unit. This tool also provides an incentive to falsify the financial statements in order to implement the year-end income targets of the company's management if not well controlled (Skousen & Wright, 2006; Lou & Wang, 2009).

Skousen & Wright (2006), Lou & Wang (2009) use the following two criteria as representative variables for financial objectives:

Return on assets (ROA)

Return on equity (ROE)

2.2.2. Factors belonging to the opportunity

This is an important group of factors belonging to the characteristics of the business, the characteristics of the board are the opportunities for individuals or organizations to easily commit fraud on the financial statements.

Characteristics of financial statements and lines of operation of the enterprise

Characteristics of financial statements and lines of operation of enterprises are one of the factors that belong to the opportunities capable of influencing the level of committing fraud on financial statements. The more complex the industry and its activities are, the more likely it is to influence fraudulent behavior on financial statements (Apostolou et al., 2001; Gramling & Myres, 2003; Moyes, 2007; Abullatif, 2013). Specifically, enterprises operating in the construction sector have some characteristics such as a long business cycle, scattered activities in a large area, the value of receivables, payables, inventories account for a large proportion of the value of assets and capital sources, construction activities are quite complex and often incur extra-budgetary expenses. The process of handover, acceptance and completion of legal procedures is prolonged. Construction activities are also susceptible to the negative effects of macroeconomic conditions. Therefore, the process of preparing financial statements at construction companies is prone to errors, or there are not enough grounds to recognize the value of construction investment.

Enterprises with a group model have many member units, can commit fraud through transactions with member units, joint ventures, associates, especially non-market transactions/short transactions to realize the goals of business leaders. Typical in the past time is the establishment of SPEs of some corporations with the purpose of creating benefits for some groups of individuals such as transferring losses, carrying out capital mobilization transactions. However, within a conglomerate, enterprises engage various audit firms to conduct audits of parent companies and subsidiaries. Auditing quality among audit firms in the

group is different. For this form, it may be a favorable opportunity to commit fraud on the financial statements in the subsidiaries, resulting in the consolidated financial statements of the parent company being subject to distortion (Apostolou et al., 2001; Gramling & Myres, 2003; Moyes, 2007; Abullatif, 2013).

In addition, enterprises operate in a variety of industries, with many distinctive professional activities. This characteristic leads to the financial statements of the business often have many indicators, complex items, business activities based on subjective judgments of the board of directors. Therefore, enterprises can take advantage of the arising transactions based on accounting estimates that may increase the chance of committing fraud to the financial statements.

According to the asymmetric information theory, under the pressure of financial objectives, management often uses unusual transactions or adjustment entries at the end of the year to increase/decrease profits to achieve business objectives set by the board of directors (Gramling & Myres, 2003, Moyes, 2007).

Characteristics of financial statements and operating lines of enterprises impacting fraudulent behavior on financial statements of enterprises can be measured through the following two criteria (Gramling & Myres, 2003; Moyes, 2007; Abullatif, 2013):

- (1) Complexity in the field of operating lines of the enterprise.
- (2) The complexity of the items in the financial statements of the enterprise.

Quality of internal control of the enterprise

The quality of the internal control system is one of the key factors influencing fraudulent behavior in the financial statements. Internal controls include the control environment, risk assessment procedures, information systems, control activities, monitoring of control activities. Fraudulent practices in the financial statements are often carried out by management and management can control internal controls to adjust the data on the financial statements through book entries (Persons, 1995; Skousen & Wright, 2006; Lou & Wang, 2009). For the control environment, enterprises do not maintain integrity and ethical values from management to employees, complex organizational structure, unclear assignment of powers and responsibilities, especially members of the management board are not independent from the board of directors, management board does not regularly supervise the process of preparing financial statements of the board of directors, regular personnel changes are a favorable condition for enterprises to commit fraud on the financial statements. The risk assessment process, in particular the assessment of the risk of fraud, is not effective in identifying the risks of fraud in the financial statements to design appropriate control procedures.

Research by Ge & McVay (2005), Ashbaugh-Skaife et al., (2007), Shenkir & Walker (2006), Doyle et al., (2007) shows that the common characteristics of enterprises with weak internal control systems are often large-scale but in the restructuring or start-up phase, or high levels of ownership concentration. And these companies lack revenue identification policies, lack of segregation of duties, many changes in organizational structure, staffing shortages, and lack of

investment in internal control. Influence of internal control system on enterprise value: research by Ohlson (2001), De Franco et al., (2005), Doyle et al., (2007), Hammersley (2011) shows that enterprises with internal control defects will affect enterprise value and share price, adversely impact profitability, growth rate of revenue. This will be an opportunity for individuals to easily commit fraud on the financial statements in order to achieve their self-interest.

The quality of internal control of the enterprise, can be measured through the following three criteria (Skousen & Wright, 2006; Lou & Wang, 2009):

(1) Control environment.

Information system

(3) Inspection and supervision activities.

The size of enterprise

Previous studies have identified corporate scale variables that have a significant influence on fraudulent behavior in the financial statements of companies. Most studies suggest that large companies are less likely to commit fraud on financial statements than small companies. This conclusion is drawn from the transnational research results of the authors: Wallace et al., (1994), Meek et al., (1995), Ahmed & Courtis (1999), Zarzeski (1996), Bushman & Smith (2001), Archambault & Archambault(2003), Kaminski et al., (2004). The above studies provide reasons for the relationship between company size and financial reporting fraud due to the need to disclose information or maybe large companies disclose more information to reduce political pressure or large companies often have more production resources to disclose more information. In addition, some studies (Bushman & Smith, 2001; Archambault & Archambault (2003) also suggest that, large enterprises often have more large investors than small enterprises, information published by them is often more sensitive to more oversight from the public, investors and government. Therefore, information published by them often receives more attention from analysts and financial experts, so the likelihood of financial reporting fraud is less than that of small businesses.

Studies on the relationship between enterprise size factors and fraudulent behavior in financial statements often have many opposite results:

The first group of viewpoints considers that the larger the size of the enterprise, the more the fraudulent behavior on the financial statements is limited, because large enterprises often have a good internal governance system, internal audit is stricter, often audited by famous companies such as Big 4 and in order to maintain reputation and reputation, these companies themselves will limit the fraudulent behavior on the financial statements (Warfield et al., 1995; Singh et al., 2001). In addition, large companies are often asked to provide more information, so they will limit fraudulent behavior on financial statements while small companies are likely not to disclose much important information that could become their advantage and cause them to commit fraudulent behavior on financial statements more (Lee & Choi, 2002).

The second group of views considers that there is a reversible relationship between the size of the business and the fraudulent behavior on the financial statements with the reasons given such as the larger the size of the business, the pressure to achieve the expected results is high, the power in negotiation with audit, the great governance power can overwhelm the internal control system (Nelson et al., 2002). In addition, large companies are often scrutinized by the market, banks, and analysts and therefore are more motivated to commit fraud on the financial statements (Richardson et al., 2002).

Enterprise size factor is measured by the following 4 criteria (Beasley, 1996; Lou & Wang, 2009)

- (1) Operating time of the enterprise.
- (2) Capital size of the enterprise.
- (3) Customer size of the business.
- (4) The size of employees of the enterprise.

Characteristics of the Board of Directors of the enterprise

The Board of Directors is responsible for overseeing the process of preparing the financial statements of the enterprise (Yatim et al., 2006). The impact of corporate management board characteristics on fraudulent behavior on financial statements of enterprises is highly focused by foreign researchers such as: Vafeas (2000); Haniffa & Cooke (2002); Klein (2002); Uzun et al.,(2004); Agrawal & Chadha (2005); Yatim et al., (2006); Efendi et al., (2007); Matousi & Gharbi (2011). These studies largely focus on the characteristics of the board of directors, such as: Size of the board of directors; Percentage of independent members in the board of directors; Percentage of board members with expertise in financial accounting; The appointment of two titles of General Director and Chairman of the board of directors; Frequency of meetings of the board of directors... Board members are not transparent with the management board: the independence and supervisory role of the board is reduced, the chance to commit fraud in these enterprises will increase. Typically, businesses are board chairpersons and general managers. This is also the underlying cause of management's assessment of control gaps that create fraud by enterprises in the world and Vietnam. The executive board is granted great authority, power is concentrated on one or several people: The delegation of more power to the executive board will increase the initiative but also create opportunities for the implementation of fraudulent acts if any.

According to the theory of representation, the board of directors appears to control the actions of managers (reducing representation costs) and to be highly efficient, the evaluation of the board structure is necessary because managers often act in their own interest and not in the interests of shareholders. The impact of board characteristics on fraudulent behavior in financial statements of enterprises has been studied by many academics. Accordingly, the characteristics of the board of directors can be measured through the following 6 criteria:

(1) Board size

Many authors such as Jensen (1993), Yermack (1996), Vafeas (2000), Abbott et al., (2006) argue that the board is too large to cause a reduction in accountability and does not exercise good control. Meanwhile, Beasley (1996) and Yermack (1996) point out that, the large-scale board is better able to control the actions of senior managers (Zahra & Pearce, 1989). The study by Fathi (2013), also gives evidence that the larger the board size, the lower the chance of fraudulent behavior on the financial statements.

(2) Number of independent board members

The existence of independent members will help to monitor the behavior of the administrator, thereby controlling fraudulent acts on the financial statements. Chen et al., (2007) research in China gives results on the reverse relationship when it is considered that the higher the percentage of independent board members, the less fraudulent behavior the company has on the financial statements. This result is consistent with the conclusion of Johari et al., (2009) in Malaysia that the higher the percentage of independent board members, the better the control of governance behavior and will reduce the likelihood of fraudulent behavior in the financial statements.

(3) Percentage of board members with expertise in financial accounting

All the above studies recognize that the board of directors has very useful financial knowledge in the management of supervision, such as: Carcello et al., (2002), Xie et al., (2003). Having financial expertise benefits board members to better understand financial reporting and financial reporting issues. Therefore, the more members of the board have financial expertise, the lower the likelihood of fraudulent data on the financial statements.

(4) The concurrent appointment of two titles of general manager and chairman of the board of directors

The roles of the general manager and the board of directors need to be separate, which will be good for the executive activity of the board of directors, because in order to operate effectively, minimize profit adjustment behavior, this separation is necessary (Code, 1992). The results of research by Mulgrew & Forker (2006) show that if the general manager is also the chairman of the board, fraudulent behavior on the financial statements is more likely to occur. The results of the study in India by Kumani & Pattanayak (2014) show that there is a favorable relationship between the concurrent two titles and fraudulent behavior in the financial statements.

(5) Number of board members with racial ties

According to research by Ghazali & Weetman (2006), Haniffa & Cooke (2002), Matousi (2011) suggested that the more members of the board of directors there are, the more likely it is that fraudulent behavior on the financial statements.

Factors of independent audit

Many studies in countries emphasize the role of auditing in protecting external investors and this is a tool to reduce representation costs (Chow, 1982; DeFond et al., 2000). Research by Ghosh (2011) in India suggests that, with developing economies and potentials such as India, the company's control system is not yet strong, so an audit role is necessary to protect investors. According to the theory of representation, Jensen & Meckling (1976) argue that the selection of a large, reputable audit firm as a way to reduce costs and enhance the role of monitoring fraudulent acts that managers may commit. Many studies on the relationship between auditing and fraudulent financial statements (Ghosh, 2011). While Fathi (2013) assessed two variables related to independent auditing are external audit firms and audit committees established by the board of directors to ensure financial accounting information and control system to reduce representation costs. However, Fakhfakh & Nasfi (2012) used only independent audit variables.

When researching independent audit variables, Fathi (2013) gives evidence that, when enterprises are audited by Big 4, the quality of accounting information will be better and reduce fraudulent behavior on financial statements because large auditing companies such as Big 4, independence, professionalism, reputation, and scale are often considered barriers to fraudulent behavior on financial statements (Xie et al., 2003). Fakhfakh & Nasfi (2012) also show, the inverse relationship between independent audit and fraudulent behavior on financial statements. Typically, when measuring the variable "independent audit", the variable will be assigned the value 1 if the enterprises are audited by Big 4 and receive the value 0 if not Big 4 (Fathi, 2013; Fakhfakh & Nasfi, 2012).

2.2.3. Attitude factor group

Attitudes are personalities, behaviors, or moral values that allow the individual to justify his or her reasons for fraud. This is the group of factors that belong to the signs related to the integrity of the manager. A manager who is not highly qualified, is poorly knowledgeable about the law and has no business ethics will easily lead to fraudulent conduct on the financial statements.

Ethical standards, lifestyle of the Board of Directors

Researchers Albrecht et al., (1986); Graham & Bedard (2003) believe that the board of directors, with weak ethics, has committed violations of financial and accounting laws in the past, plus the board of directors has a lavish lifestyle, can take all measures to achieve financial goals, which does not exclude material misstatement of the financial statements.

The ethics and lifestyle standards of the board of directors are reflected in the following four criteria (Graham & Bedard, 2003):

- (1) The board of directors has a history of violating the law.
- (2) Board of Directors has weak morals, luxurious lifestyle.
- (3) The Board of Directors is independent and exclusive.
- (4) The board of directors is overly ambitious about the business results.

Qualifications of the board of directors

Qualifications are reflected in qualifications, work experience and continuous updating of knowledge to gain an in-depth understanding of the opportunities and risks that can happen to your business, since most business areas of enterprises are very diverse, transaction nature and complex items. Leaders with low education or in an unprofessional training environment may be at risk of violating industry and business regulations, leading to a high risk of financial reporting errors. The management of highly qualified enterprises will help to predict and recognize risks related to their enterprises, detect material misstatements to prevent fraudulent behavior in the financial statements (Moyes, 2007). The professional qualifications of the board of directors are reflected in the following four measurement criteria:

- (1) Train the right major.
- (2) Full knowledge update.
- (3) Ability to study and update information.
- (4) Work experience in the industry.

Awareness and understanding of the law of the Board of Directors

Awareness and understanding of the law of the Board of Directors have a great influence on the fraudulent behavior on the financial statements. When the board of directors has a good awareness and understanding of the law, the likelihood of fraud on the financial statements is very low and on the contrary, the awareness and understanding of the legal regulations of the board of directors is not high, the probability of fraud on the financial statements is large (Hatem Elsharawy, 2006). The awareness of law compliance of the BOARD OF DIRECTORS can be assessed through the background of each individuals.(Apostolou et al., 2001; Smith et al., 2005; Moyes, 2007; Abullatif, 2013). Legal awareness and understanding of the board of directors includes the following criteria:

- (1) The board of directors' understanding of the law.
- (2) The legal compliance of the board of directors.
- (3) Awareness and understanding of the board of directors on the relevant applicable legal regulations.

Attitude and professionalism of the board of directors

It is the responsibility of the board of directors to supervise effective internal control in order to detect and prevent fraudulent acts on the financial statements. However, the lack of seriousness and unprofessionalism that has caused management to deliberately fail to correct or untimely correct can be indicative of management restricting internal controls or taking advantage of internal control gaps to commit fraud (Smith et al., 2005). The Board of Directors has the independence and authority to manage and intervene in accounting policies, accounting estimates will increase the variances in the financial statements of the business (Gramling & Myres, 2003; Abullatif, 2013).

The attitude and professionalism of the management include (Gramling & Myres, 2003; Abullatif, 2013):

- (1) Integrity, objectivity, fairness.
- (2) The Board of Directors acts to control internal control.
- (3) The Board of Directors has disagreements with the auditor, limiting the scope of the audit.
- (4) The board of directors does not consciously adhere to the principles and regulations of the profession.

3. CONCLUSION:

Fraud in general and fraud on financial statements of enterprises in particular are increasingly developed, sophisticated and difficult to detect, manifested in various forms, from simple to complex, corresponding to the development of society and human perception. Therefore, in order to detect, prevent and minimize fraudulent behavior on financial statements of enterprises, it is necessary to understand, master and control the factors affecting fraudulent behavior, which can improve the quality of financial reporting information. This study has focused on synthesizing and pointing out the main factors affecting fraudulent behavior in the financial statements of enterprises in theoretical terms. The study also has the limitation that the influence of each factor on fraudulent behavior on financial statements of enterprises has not been quantified in practice. Future studies can expand the objectives and scope of research and apply appropriate research methods to obtain more comprehensive assessment results.

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